

POLITENESS IN THE COVID-19 WORKPLACE: THE CASE OF UNIVERSITY AMERICAN COLLEGE SKOPJE

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the level of politeness in the workplace during the COVID-19 pandemic by using the speech acts of request, apology and compliment in English. The organization that is subject to research is University American College Skopje - a private higher-education institution in the Republic of North Macedonia. Organizational communication is essential for the performance of and within one organization and is a crucial part of employees' motivation, employees' retention, positive performance and positive financial outcomes of the organization. On the other hand, being polite in the workplace and following proper workplace etiquette can help managers and workers function as a unit. Hence, as language is the main tool of communication, its effectiveness is analyzed and determined through language analysis done on the use of three speech acts: request, apology and compliment, which are considered to be most commonly used in an organizational setting.

The research is conducted with participants who hold administrative and managerial positions at UACS. They are invited to electronically respond to six different situations, which ask them to use the speech acts that are subject to this research: once in a conversation with their fellow colleague on the same level, and then when conversing with their superior - for the administrative positions, and with their subordinate - for the management-positioned respondents. The situations given in the questionnaire are constructed to seem natural for the respondents' particular working environment.

For better communication to be achieved, normal circumstances in life and business always recommend using polite language, but the new COVID-19 pandemic, with its urge for physical distancing and isolation, calls for mandatory politeness, to ensure people's mental wellbeing and successful organizational communication.

The research shows that, in this pandemic, when communicating through the three speech acts, the UACS employees are highly polite in their organizational communication.

KEYWORDS: *politeness, workplace, pandemic, speech acts, organizational communication, UACS case study*

INTRODUCTION

Over the past several years, the interest in the process of internal communication within an organization has increased due to the importance of this process and its effect on the overall organizational performance. Organizational communication has been connected to many positive outcomes, such as: employee job satisfaction, effective daily operations, financial success of the organization and many more.

When speaking about effective organizational communication, the first thing to look at is the language used in the process. Language analysis can give information about the tone of the communication, how the language is used, what is used to communicate, and more. This type of language analysis can be done using the speech act theory which will further help investigate the effectiveness of a particular communication practice. The effectiveness can be investigated from several aspects, one of which is the use of the politeness strategies. This research will focus on the use of politeness strategies with the speech acts of requests, apologies and compliments, as one of the mostly used speech acts in organizational communication.

Searle (1976) maintains that requests, as speech acts, belong to the group of directives and are used when the speaker wishes to encourage the listener to perform some action. When a speaker is using the speech act of request, he/she has to use adequate vocabulary and strategy so that the listener is easily persuaded to do the action in question. In this paper,

the speech act of request will be analyzed as used in upward, downward and horizontal communication.

The second speech act to be described and analyzed is the speech act of apology. This speech act belongs to the group of expressives (Searle, 1976) and, when used, expresses regret for a certain action. There are different strategies of using this speech act, which will be further discussed in this paper. The direction of using the language to apologize, which will be analyzed, is in upward, downward and horizontal communication.

The last speech act to be analyzed is the speech act of compliment. Compliments are essential in the process of employee motivation and are mainly used to give credit for someone's abilities and qualities; therefore, it is important to see how they are used within one organization. Compliments belong to the group of expressives (Searle, 1976) and, as speech acts that act as a politeness strategy, are fundamental in investigating the effectiveness of the communication process within one organization.

Aiming to achieve its purpose, the paper will try to answer to three research questions:

RQ1: Which directness strategy is applied when using the speech acts of request, apology, and compliment in upward, downward and horizontal communication?

RQ2: What are the differences and/or similarities when using the speech acts of request, apology and compliment between the management and administration representatives?

RQ3: What is the overall effectiveness of the organizational communication at UACS seen from the perspective of management and administration level?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

There has been an increasing interest in researching the internal organizational discourse, its importance and its effect on the employees' and organizational performance. Researchers have focused their interest on the core means of communication - the language and its functions in the communication process, as well as the theory of speech acts. However, it appears that there is limited data on the effective use of the speech acts in organizational setting.

The speech act theory originates from philosophy and deals with the intention of the speaker as well as the relation between utterances. It implies that the linguistic analysis of text/utterance is the core function of interpreting utterances, and focuses on linguistic competence as a condition for successful performance of a speech act.

Austin (1962) classified the illocutionary acts in five classes: verdictives (include acts of giving verdict such as reckoning, diagnosing, assessing), exercitives (include acts of exerting power, rights or influence, such as appointing, voting, ordering, warning), commissives (include acts that commit the speaker to doing something such as promising, consenting, opposing), behabitives (include acts that clarify reasons, arguments, such as denying, stating, describing), expositives (include acts related to attitudes and social behavior, such as apologizing, congratulating, thanking). Austin's theory was further developed by Searle (1976) who focused on the illocutionary speech acts. His categorization is based

on particular principles that distinguish the acts from one another.

Bach (2008) argues that there should be a distinction between the linguistic or the semantic meaning of the word, and the pragmatic meaning that the word has when uttered in a particular context. The study of pragmatics concerns itself with the "acts of using language", which should be separated from the study of semantics that is concerned with the linguistic meaning of the language. The meaning of the words can be semantically different and when uttered by a speaker in a certain context. For example, one can give thanks by using the words 'thank you', or by saying 'I am really appreciative of your help yesterday'. Either way, the attitude of giving thanks is expressed.

In a close relation to the essence of the speech act theory is the notion of pragmatic competence as part of the study of pragmatics. Pragmatic competence is linked to the ability to recognize the particular speech act and respond accordingly, therefore communicate effectively. Pragmatics, as an area of study, deals with the meaning of words and utterances that go beyond their linguistic meaning or the meaning found in the dictionaries. More specifically, it explains what one word or utterance means based on the norms of one society or the particular context in which the interaction happens. Thus, good knowledge of the norms of the society or the context in which the conversation happens helps the speaker to communicate effectively as well as to effectively recognize the message coming from the other interlocutor (Yule, 1996, cited in Vaneva and Ivanovska, 2018).

THE SPEECH ACT OF REQUESTING

Al-Nayli (2017) claims that the speech act of request is among the most investigated features of the language, and it belongs to the speech act of directives. The

act of request is always beneficial for the one who is requesting it or for the speaker. It can be expressed directly or indirectly. With direct requests, the listener is clearly given the role of the action doer (e.g., *You need to finish that report by tomorrow morning.*), whereas with indirect requests the role of an action doer has not been clearly assigned and therefore it is left to the listener to understand the hint and do what is asked (e.g., *The data in this report is not correct.*). When the requester chooses to make a direct request, he/she will use a performative or imperative form, thus he/she will issue an order. The requester may choose to use modal verbs which will weaken the strength of the order; however, it will still remain to be an order. When making a direct request, the listener may interpret it as a violation of their freedom of action or even as a power play. If the speaker wants to avoid this kind of interpretation of the speech act, he/she may resort to making an indirect request.

In their study, Blum Kulka and Olshtain (1984) elaborate on strategies of making requests based on different aspects. One aspect is from the point of directness or indirectness. Namely, they distinguish the following strategies:

The most direct or explicit requests that are in the form of imperatives:

e.g., “*Clean the kitchen!*”

The conventionally indirect level or, in other words, these are requests that have given preconditions for its performance:

e.g., “*Would you mind finishing that for me?*”

The non-conventional indirect level, open-ended strategies or hints:

e.g., “*Why is the window open?*”

Blum-Kulka further elaborates on the linguistic forms with which the act of

requests can be made and these are as follows:

1. Declaratives can be used with any speech act. Specifically, in this case, the declaratives can be used to make a request as in the following examples:

e.g., *I think you have forgotten to open the window in my office.*

As mentioned before, the declaratives can be used with modal verbs or semi-modal verbs to express requests, which will down tone the strength of the request in terms of giving an order.

2. Imperatives are used to make requests when the request needs to be understood as an order. Unless the speaker wants to sound kinder when giving the order, he/she can add ‘please’ to the request.

e.g., 1 *Come to the meeting to take notes.*

e.g., 2 *Please come to the meeting to take notes.*

3. Interrogatives are used to make requests with yes/no questions or with conditional interrogatives. They can be also used as down graders to the imposition that the speech act of request invokes.

e.g., *Do you mind taking this assignment from Ana?*

Would you take this assignment from Ana if I asked you?

The study of Yunus and Thuruvan (2017) dealt with the speech act of request in a classroom setting, among students and teachers, aiming to show who is using direct/indirect requests, when and with whom. It showed that students are less polite when requesting something from their fellow students and more polite when requesting something from the teacher, and, on the other hand, the

teacher uses less polite requests when requesting something from the students. This result shows that the ones who are in the upper hierarchical level are more prone to using direct requests or less polite requests. If this result was to be applied in an organizational setting, the employees would be using less polite requests to their fellow employees and more polite or indirect requests to their superiors, and the superiors would be using direct requests to their subordinates.

However, it is legitimate to consider the idea that even when superiors are requesting something from their subordinates, they should use polite requests in order to maintain the enthusiasm of the subordinate and to avoid any demotivation. In their study, Clark and Schunk (1980) have elaborated on indirect or polite requests, and have distinguished several categories of polite requests, according to their level of politeness. The categories are as follows:

- Permission – *May I ask you to finish this by noon?*

Here the requester is basically asking permission from the requestee to allow him/her to ask something from them, which grants a certain power to the requestee. This type of request is one of the politest ones and it benefits the requestee.

- Imposition – *Would you mind finishing this report by noon?*

In this case, the requester admits that he/she imposes when requesting something. This type of request is relatively polite and benefits the requestee.

- Ability – *Can you finish this report by noon?*

Here the requester is asking for the ability of the requestee if he/she is able to do a certain action. This allows the requestee to avoid this action due to their inability

to do it, but at the same time it may imply that the requester is not completely sure of their ability to do the requested action. This type of request is considered to be as polite as the previous two.

- Memory – *Have I already asked you to do this report?*

This request expresses subtle demand when something has been asked from the requestee and it hasn't been done yet, so the requester would kindly remind them by reflecting on memory. This type of request is considered to be less polite than the first three.

- Commitment – *Will you finish this report by noon?*

This request is asking for commitment from the requestee. By obligating himself/herself to do the requested action, the requestee is granting power to the requester later to demand the completion of their obligation. It is considered to be less polite than the others.

- Obligation – *Shouldn't you finish this report by noon?*

This type of request is the least polite of all. The requester is asking the requestee whether he/she is under obligation to do a certain action. By using the modal 'shouldn't', the requester is implying that the requestee has failed in doing the action in question, i.e., their obligation.

Another aspect they use to look into the strategies for making requests is the so-called strategy 'point of view' that Blum-Kulka and Olshtain (1984) elaborate in their study. Having in mind that in each request there is a requester, requestee and the action requested to be done, the requester can emphasize a different element of his request and by that manipulate the directness of the request. As per this distinction, there are four categories of requests:

Hearer-oriented – e.g. *Could you finish*

that report by noon?

Speaker-oriented – e.g. *Could I have that finished by noon?*

Speaker- and hearer-oriented – e.g. *Could we have that finished by noon?*

Impersonal – e.g. *Could this be finished by noon?*

The Speech Act of Apology

Aydin (2013) researched the speech act of apology from a point of directness. In this term, apologies can be either direct or indirect. Direct apologies are explicit expressions that convey meaning of having regrets about something. These apologies would normally contain the phrases “be sorry”, “apologize”, “excuse”. On the other hand, indirect apologies are not expressed that explicitly but rather in the form of explanations, acknowledgement of culpability; offer to make amends, or a promise to behave well. The indirect apologies are considered to be more polite than the direct ones; however, in some situations, these apologies can lead to ambiguity. Whenever using either strategy for apology, it is important for the speaker to be aware of the culture, profile of the receiver and the speaker-receiver mutual relationships, so that the apology is effective and understood in the intended manner. When apologizing, the speaker chooses the intensity of the apology. So, they can use adverbs to intensify the apology, such as: “*I am very deeply sorry*”, therefore trying to maximize the regret that the wrong doer is feeling. Or, to the contrary, if the speaker is apologizing as a formality but not feeling it, then he would say as little as possible to express the regret. This can be done by minimizing the regret, or the offence, or rejecting the responsibility completely. Having said that, according to Cohen and Olshtain, 1983 (cited in Aydin, 2013), there are five apology strategies that go from the most direct or ex-

PLICIT to the most indirect one. The strategies are as follows:

- Direct apology – includes the verbs such as *sorry, excuse, forgive*;
- Explanation: nonspecific explanation (e.g., *There has been a lot going on in my life*), or specific explanation (e.g., *I could not catch the bus*);
- Responsibility – implicit responsibility (e.g., *I was sure I did it right*), lack of intent (e.g., *I did not mean to*), self-deficiency (e.g., *How could I be so blind*), self-blame (e.g., *It’s my fault*);
- Repair – unspecified (e.g., *How can I fix that?*), or specified (e.g., *Let me buy a new one for you*);
- Promise of forbearance – (e.g., *It won’t happen again*).

The Speech Act of Compliment

As speech acts, compliments belong to Searle’s (1976) group of expressives. The purpose of the given compliment can be different depending on the reasons behind the speaker’s agenda. In Duan’s study (2011), several purposes are mentioned that the compliments as speech acts serve. They can be used to start a conversation, to break the ice in an uncomfortable situation, to praise someone for their professional or private qualities, or to simply keep solidarity between people. When speaking about speech acts in organizational communication, it is inevitable to mention the motivation purpose of the compliments, especially when given from superior to subordinate. However, it is important that the compliments are given to the right person and at the right moment, in order to avoid any negative effect that can influence the performance of the person that is being complimented to.

Farenkia (2012) argues there are three strategies to express compliments:

direct compliments, indirect compliments and compliments with external modification. Direct compliments are expressed in an unambiguous or explicit manner with positive note, expressed directly to the addressee. Indirect compliments are expressed in a more ambiguous way that requires certain level of supposition by the addressee in order to get the intended meaning of the compliment. Indirect compliments can also be expressed to an addressee that is connected to the person to whom the compliment is given. (e.g., *Your little boy is cute*). The third strategy, external modification, refers to the acts that are said before or after the direct compliments, serving a purpose of intensifying or mitigating. (e.g., *Hi, I am Ana and I loved your book*). As per Farenkia's findings, the most commonly used compliment strategy is direct compliments. When seen from organizational communication perspective, same as with all the other speech acts, it is most beneficial when using direct strategies to communicate a certain message so that the addressee can benefit from the message given to them.

Another categorization of compliments is the one on simple and complex compliments made in Solodka and Perea's study (2018). According to this study, simple compliments are expressions that consist of one sentence or a single compliment (e.g., *Well done!*) that creates the whole meaning of the compliment. On the other hand, complex compliments consist of more than one sentence, and there is more than one word that creates the meaning (e.g., *I am so happy to have an amazing employee like you. I saw the presentation, it was outstanding!*).

METHODS

This paper is designed as a case study, conducted at University American College Skopje (UACS), North Macedonia. As

a method, the case study allows in-depth exploration of a certain phenomenon in a given context (Harrison et al. 2017), such as the case of UACS, where the language in a form of particular speech acts is investigated within the process of organizational communication. With the case study method, the researcher collects qualitative data from one chosen unit on a certain topic, which is later subject to analysis. The unit of analysis will define the case, and this can be community, organization, counties, particular groups, and others (Tellis, 1997). Further, within the unit, the researcher will take a representative sample that will provide qualitative data on the given subject. The qualitative data that is collected during the research can lead to results which show "an in-depth understanding of behaviors, processes, practices, and relationships in context" (Harrison et al., 2017).

In terms of the approach, the case study can be exploratory, explanatory and descriptive. This research was exploratory by approach, as its goal was to explore the language that is used within one organization through particular speech acts used in particular situations. In this research, qualitative methods were applied, and collected data was analyzed according to previously set parameters.

The technique used for this research is questionnaire. The target groups are respondents from the management structure and representatives of the administration. A situational questionnaire in English language was built for each group with open-ended questions to provide qualitative data. The questionnaires consist of two situations for each speech act; one in horizontal communication and another one in upward or downward communication respectively.

The questionnaire was sent to 6 representatives of the management and 11 representatives of the administration. We received feedback from all 6 management

representatives, and from 5 administration employees, therefore this was the final sample that provided data for analysis in this research. The respondents were informed about the goal of the research and were invited to participate voluntarily and anonymously.

The collected data was analyzed and described by using tables, charts, numbers and percentages, as well as textual analysis complementing the numbers, tables and charts.

RESULTS

This segment of the study presents the findings of the questionnaire with regards to three research questions:

RQ1: Which directness strategy is applied when using the speech acts of requests, apologies, and compliments in upward, downward and horizontal communication?

RQ2: What are the differences or similarities when using the speech acts of requests, apologies and compliments between the management and administration representatives?

RQ3: What is the overall effectiveness of the organizational communication at UACS seen from the perspective of management and administration level?

The qualitative data gathered from 11 participants' responses to the questionnaire was analyzed by means of descriptive statistics and is presented in this chapter.

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

The participants that provided their responses are all employees at UACS. One group of them belongs to the administration section and the other group belongs to the management. Both males and females at different age were included in the research. The complete demographic data is presented in Table 1 below.

Hence, 54.55% of the participants were females and 45.45% were males. Out of the 11 participants who provided their responses, 54.55% belong to the management group, and 45.45% belong to the administration group.

DIRECTNESS STRATEGY USED IN UPWARD, DOWNWARD AND HORIZONTAL COMMUNICATION, WHEN USING THE SPEECH ACTS OF REQUEST, APOLOGY AND COMPLIMENT AT UACS

This section presents the results of the questionnaire with regards to the first research question: *Which directness strategy is applied when using the speech acts of requests, apologies, and compliments in upward, downward and horizontal*

Table 1
Demographic data

No.	Items	Number	Percentage
1.	<i>Gender</i>		
	Female	6	54.55%
	Male	5	45.45%
2.	<i>Hierarchy level</i>		
	Management	6	54.55%
	Administration	5	45.45%

communication? Since the directness strategy of the speech acts makes the basic distinction whether a speech act is polite or impolite, and “[o]ne of the most effective ways to ensure and accomplish communication is the use of politeness strategies” (Shabeeb and Jibreen, 2008, p.10), it was first necessary to research the directness strategy that the employees at UACS apply when using the speech acts of requests, apologies and compliments in the three different layers of hierarchy (see Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4).

When it comes to using the speech acts in downward communication, in the case of the speech act of request, the majority of 66.67% used the indirect strategy. In the cases of the speech act of apology and compliment, the same percentage of majority (83.33%) used the direct strategy.

Overall, in terms of directness strategy, in the case of downward communication,

the majority or 66.67% of the participants would apply the direct strategy. The complete result can be seen in Table 2.

Next, in the case of upward communication, or communication that flows from the subordinate to the superior, the responses show that when subordinates use the speech act of request with their superiors generally (80% of the participants) use the indirect strategy to request something from their superior. In the cases of apologies and compliments, the numbers are identical. The majority of them or 60% would use the indirect strategy. Overall, when it comes to upward communication in the cases of the speech acts of requests, apologies and compliments, the majority of the participants or 66.67% would use the indirect strategy; all the numbers are presented in Table 3.

Table 2
Use of directness strategy in downward communication

Speech act	Directness strategy			
	Number		Percentage	
	Direct strategy	Indirect strategy	Direct strategy	Indirect strategy
Request	2	4	33.33%	66.67%
Apology	5	1	83.33%	16.67%
Compliment	5	1	83.33%	16.67%
			66.67%	33.33%

Table 3
Use of directness strategy in upward communication

Speech act	Directness strategy			
	Number		Percentage	
	Direct strategy	Indirect strategy	Direct strategy	Indirect strategy
Request	1	4	20%	80%
Apology	2	3	40%	60%
Compliment	2	3	40%	60%
	5	10	33.33%	66.67%

Table 4*Use of directness strategy in horizontal communication*

Speech act	Directness strategy			
	Number		Percentage	
	Direct strategy	Indirect strategy	Direct strategy	Indirect strategy
Request	5	6	45.45%	54.55%
Apology	4	7	36.36%	63.64%
Compliment	8	3	72.73%	27.27%
	17	16	51.52%	48.48%

Lastly, in the case of horizontal communication, or the communication that happens between two colleagues on the same hierarchical level, the responses show that 51.52% of the participants prefer the direct strategy, and 48.48% would apply the indirect strategy when using these speech acts (see Table 4).

DIFFERENCES AND/OR SIMILARITIES WHEN USING THE SPEECH ACTS OF REQUESTS, APOLOGIES AND COMPLIMENTS BETWEEN THE MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION REPRESENTATIVES

This section of the study answers to the second research question: *What are the differences and/or similarities when using the speech acts of requests, apologies and compliments between the management and administration representatives?* The answers to this research question will help determine if there are any differences and/or similarities in the language used in the cases of two different hierarchical levels in the organization that might eventually affect the effectiveness of the communication process. (see Table 5, Table 6, Table 7, Table 8, Table 9, Table 10, Table 11, Table 12 and Table 13; and Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4).

In this section, the speech act of request is investigated through the level of directness (direct and indirect), through its form (declarative, imperative and interrogative), through the strategies of

the indirect request (permission, imposition, ability, memory, commitment and obligation), and through the orientation of the request (hearer-oriented, speaker-oriented, impersonal orientation and both hearer- and speaker-oriented). Table 5 gives picture of the language used by the representatives of the management in two instances: one in horizontal communication and the other in downward communication. The responses of the management representatives show both similarities and distinctive differences when it comes to using this speech act with their fellow colleagues, and, on the other hand, with their subordinates. The direct request was used by 16.67% of the participants with a fellow colleague, whereas 33.33% of them used it with a subordinate. In the case of indirect requests, 83.33% of the participants used it with a fellow colleague, and 66.67% of them used it with a subordinate. When it comes to the form of the request, 16.67% used it as a declarative request with a fellow colleague, and 83.33% used the same form with their subordinate. The imperative form was not used in any case. There is a big difference in the use of interrogative form of request, or 83.33% of the participants used it with their fellow colleague, and only 16.67% used it with a subordinate. With regards to the strategies of indirect requests, when using indirect request with their fellow colleagues, the management representatives have used three strategies: permission with

Table 5
Use of the speech act of request by the management representatives

Use of the speech act of request by:	Use of the speech act of request with colleagues on the same hierarchical level		Use of the speech act of request with subordinates	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Directness				
Direct request	1	16.67%	2	33.33%
Indirect request	5	83.33%	4	66.67%
Form				
Declarative	1	16.67%	5	83.33%
Imperative	/	/	/	/
Interrogative	5	83.33%	1	16.67%
Indirect request strategies				
Permission	1	16.67%	/	/
Imposition	2	33.33%	/	/
Ability	2	33.33%	2	33.33%
Memory	/	/	/	/
Commitment	/	/	1	16.67%
Obligation	/	/	1	16.67%
Orientation				
Hearer-oriented	6	100%	4	66.67%
Speaker-oriented	/	/	/	/
Impersonal orientation	/	/	1	16.67%
Speaker- and hearer-oriented	/	/	1	16.67%

16.67%, imposition with 33.33%, and ability with 33.33%. On the other hand, when these same respondents used indirect request with their subordinates, they used the following strategies: ability with 33.33%, commitment with 16.67%, and obligation with 16.67%. Lastly, in terms of orientation, the requests that this group used with their fellow colleagues were 100% hearer-oriented, whereas the requests they used with their subordinates were 66.67% hearer-oriented, 16.67% with impersonal orientation and 16.67% with both speaker- and hearer-orientation.

The next section shows the use of the speech act of request by the administration representatives, both with their superiors and their fellow colleagues. The responses that these participants gave in the two situations have substantial

difference. Namely, 80% of the participants used the direct request with their fellow colleagues and only 25% of them used direct request with their superiors. The use of the indirect request in the case with their fellow colleagues is represented only with 20% of the participants and in the case with their superiors with 75% of them. In terms of the form of the request, 20% of them would use declarative form with their fellow colleagues and 80% of them would use the interrogative form on this same level. On the other hand, when it comes to their superiors, 75% of them would declaratively form the request and 25% of them would use the request in interrogative form. Those who used indirect request used the following strategies: imposition in 20% of the cases with their fellow colleagues, permission in 50% of the cases with their superiors, and commitment in 25% of

Table 6*Use of the speech act of request by the administration representatives*

<i>Use of the speech act of request by:</i>	<i>Use of the speech act of request with colleagues on the same hierarchical level</i>		<i>Use of the speech act of request with superiors</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Directness				
Direct request	4	80%	1	25%
Indirect request	1	20%	3	75%
Form				
Declarative	1	20%	3	75%
Imperative	/	/	/	
Interrogative	4	80%	1	25%
Indirect request strategies				
Permission	/	/	2	66.66%
Imposition	1	20%	/	/
Ability	/	/	/	/
Memory	/	/	/	/
Commitment	/	/	1	33.33%
Obligation	/	/	/	/
Orientation				
Hearer-oriented	5	100%	/	/
Speaker-oriented	/	/	4	100%
Impersonal orientation	/	/	/	/
Speaker- and hearer-oriented	/	/	/	/

the cases with their superiors. Finally, in terms of orientation, 100% of the participants used hearer-oriented request with their fellow colleagues, and 100% of them used speaker-oriented request in the situation with their superior.

Note: One member of this group didn't use any request in the situation with her superior, so this participant is not accounted in the results shown in Table 6.

When examining the overall use of the speech act of request by both management and administration representatives, the results show significant differences between the two groups. First, in the case of using direct or indirect request, the responses of the management group show that 25% of them use the speech act of request in its direct form, and the majority or 75% of them use the indirect form of the speech act. On the

other hand, the administration representatives said that 55.56% of them use the direct request both with their superiors and fellow colleagues, and 44.44% of them responded with an indirect request in the given situations. It is interesting here that one member of the administration group, in the case of using the speech act of request with the superior, responded that the request would not be made at all, thus in the numbers of this speech act this member is excluded in one situation. Next, regarding the form of the speech act, the management representatives are equally divided between the declarative and interrogative form of this speech act, or 50% of them would use the declarative form and the other 50% would use the interrogative form. On the other hand, the situation is similar, or 44.44% of the administration representatives would use the declarative form of

Table 7

Comparison of overall use of the speech act of request between the management and administration representatives

Use of the speech act of request by:	Management group		Administration group	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Directness				
Direct request	3	25%	5	55.56%
Indirect request	9	75%	4	44.44%
Form				
Declarative	6	50%	4	44.44%
Imperative				
Interrogative	6	50%	5	55.56%
Indirect request strategies				
Permission	1	11.11%	2	50%
Imposition	2	22.22%	1	25%
Ability	4	44.44%	/	
Memory	/		/	
Commitment	1	11.11%	1	25%
Obligation	1	11.11%	/	
Orientation				
Hearer oriented	10	83.33%	5	55.56%
Speaker oriented	/		4	44.44%
Impersonal orientation	1	8.33%		
Speaker and hearer oriented	1	8.33%		

the speech act, and the minor majority or 55.56% would use the interrogative form of this speech act. When it comes to those who would use indirect request, there are several strategies that can be used and the level of politeness is seen upon them when this type of request is used. Namely, the first strategy is the permission strategy, and responses showed that 8.33% of the management would use it when using indirect request. This same strategy is used by 22.22% of the administration representatives. The next strategy is the one called imposition and is used by 16.67% of the management representatives and 11.11% of the administration representatives. The strategy called ability is used by 33.33% of the management

representatives, and none of the administration representatives have used this strategy. The commitment strategy is used by 8.33% of the management group and 11.11% of the administration group. Lastly, the obligation strategy is seen in the indirect requests of 8.33% of the management representatives and none of the administration group has used this strategy. With regards to orientation in the speech act of request, 83.33% of the requests made by the management representatives were hearer-orientated. In the other group, 55.56% made requests with hearer orientation, and 44.44% made requests with speaker orientation. A visual presentation of these results is shown with Figure 2.

Figure 2

Visual presentation of the overall use of the speech act of request by both groups

Note: DR – Direct request; IR – Indirect request; Dec – Declarative form; Imp – Imperative form; Int – Interrogative form; P – Permission; I – Imposition; A – Ability; M – memory; C – Commitment; O – Obligation; HO – Hearer-oriented; SO – Speaker-oriented; IO – Impersonal orientation; SHO – Speaker and hearer orientation.

The second speech act investigated is the speech act of apology. The speech act of apology in this section is investigated through the level of directness (direct and indirect apology), and the four strategies that can be used in this speech act: explanation, responsibility, repair and promise of forbearance. The results are

shown in three tables (see Table 8, Table 9, and Table 10).

The first table (Table 8) shows the responses of the management representatives with regards to the use of the speech act of apology with their fellow colleague in one instance and in another instance with their subordinates. In the first instance, the majority of this group of employees responded with direct apology in 66.67% of the cases. On the other hand, when it comes to apologizing to their subordinates, 83.33% responded with direct apology. With regards to the strategies that can be used in the speech act of apology, most of the respondents or 66.67% used the explanation strategy.

Table 8

Use of the speech act of apology by the management representatives

Use of the speech act of apology by:	Use of the speech act of apology with colleagues on the same hierarchical level		Use of the speech act of apology with subordinates	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Directness				
Direct apology	4	66.67%	5	83.33%
Indirect apology	2	33.33%	1	16.67%
Apology strategy				
Explanation	4	66.67%	1	16.67%
Responsibility				
Repair	1	16.67%	6	100%
Promise of forbearance				

In the other scenario with their subordinates, explanation strategy was used in 16.67% of the responses and 100% of them included the repair strategy in their apology.

Table 9 presents the results from the responses that the administration representatives provided in the cases of the speech act of apology with their superiors and their fellow administration colleagues. According to the first category of analysis, in the case with their fellow colleagues, 100% of the respondents answered with direct apology. In the other case with their superiors, 60% of them responded with indirect request. In terms of the strategies, in the case with

their fellow colleagues, the participants used the explanation strategy in 60% of the cases, the repair strategy in 40% of the cases and the promise of forbearance strategy in 40% of the cases. In the other situation with their superiors, the respondents mostly used the explanation strategy in 80% of the cases.

In the overall comparison between the two groups of participants, the results show that the management group used the direct apology in 75% of the cases. The results of the administration group are similar, or 70% of them used the direct apology. In terms of the strategies used in their apologies, the management group uses the explanation strategy in

Table 9

Use of the speech act of apology by the administration representatives

<i>Use of the speech act of apology by:</i>	<i>Use of the speech act of apology with colleagues on the same hierarchical level</i>		<i>Use of the speech act of apology with superiors</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Directness				
Direct apology	5	100%	2	40%
Indirect apology			3	60%
Apology strategy				
Explanation	3	60%	4	80%
Responsibility			1	20%
Repair	2	40%	2	40%
Promise of forbearance	2	40%	1	20%

Table 10

Comparison of overall use of the speech act of apology between the management and administration representatives

<i>Use of the speech act of apology by:</i>	<i>Management group</i>		<i>Administration group</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Directness				
Direct apology	9	75%	7	70%
Indirect apology	3	25%	3	30%
Apology strategy				
Explanation	5	41.67%	7	70%
Responsibility	/	/	1	10%
Repair	7	58.33%	4	40%
Promise of forbearance	/	/	3	30%

41.67% of the cases and the repair strategy in 58.33% of the cases. The administration group mainly used the explana-

tion strategy in 70% of the cases. A visual presentation of these results is shown with Figure 3.

Figure 3

Visual presentation of the overall use of the speech act of apology by both groups

Note: DA – Direct apology; IA – Indirect Apology; Exp. – Explanation strategy; Res. – Responsibility strategy; Rep. – Repair strategy; PoF – Promise of forbearance strategy.

The last speech act investigated is the speech act of compliment. The speech act of compliment in this section is analysed through the levels of directness (direct, indirect and compliment with external modification) and the complexity (simple and complex). Same as with the other two speech acts, there are three tables (see Table 11, Table 12, and Table 13) that show the responses of the management group in both situations, administration group in both situations, and overall use by both groups, respectively. Table 11 shows the numbers and percentages of the use of this speech act by the management group in horizontal and downward communication. In the first scenario, with their fellow colleagues, 33.33% of

them responded with direct compliment, 16.67% responded with indirect compliment and 50% of them responded with compliment with external modification. In the second scenario, with their subordinates, 50% of them responded with direct compliment, 16.67% responded with indirect compliment and 33.33% responded with compliment with external modification. In both scenarios, 100% of the participants used complex compliments.

Table 12 presents the results from the responses of the administration group using the speech act of compliment in two scenarios: one with their fellow colleagues and another with their superiors. In the first scenario, where they had to use compliment with their fellow colleague, 60% of them responded with direct compliment and 40% responded with indirect compliment. In the second scenario, where they used this speech

Table 11

Use of the speech act of compliment by the management representatives

<i>Use of the speech act of compliment by:</i>	<i>Use of the speech act of compliment in the case with colleagues on the same level</i>		<i>Use of the speech act of compliment in the case with their subordinates</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Directness				
Direct compliment	2	33.33%	3	50%
Indirect compliment	1	16.67%	1	16.67%
Compliment with external modification	3	50%	2	33.33%
Complexity				
Simple compliment	/	/	/	/
Complex compliment	6	100%	6	100%

Table 12

Use of the speech act of compliment by the administration representatives

<i>Use of the speech act of compliment by:</i>	<i>Use of the speech act of compliment in the case with colleagues on the same level</i>		<i>Use of the speech act of compliment in the case with their superiors</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Directness				
Direct compliment	3	60%	1	20%
Indirect compliment	2	40%	3	60%
Compliment with external modification	/	/	1	20%
Complexity				
Simple compliment				
Complex compliment	5	100%	5	100%

Table 13

Comparison of the overall use of the speech act of compliment between the management and administration group

<i>Use of the speech act of compliment by:</i>	<i>Management group</i>		<i>Administration group</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Directness				
Direct compliment	5	41.67%	4	40%
Indirect compliment	2	16.67%	5	50%
Compliment with external modification	5	41.67%	1	10%
Complexity				
Simple compliment				
Complex compliment	12	100%	10	100%

pliments with external modification equally, or 41.67% of them. On the other hand, the administration group responded with direct compliment in 40% of the cases, with indirect compliment in 50% of the cases, and only 10% of them would

use the compliment with external modification. Both groups, in 100% of the cases used complex compliments. A visual of the overall use of this speech act by both groups is presented with Figure 4.

Figure 4

Visual presentation of the overall use of the speech act of compliment by management and administration group

Note: DC - Direct compliment; IC - Indirect compliment; CEM – Compliment with external modification; SC – Simple compliment; CC – Complex compliment;

3.4 The overall effectiveness of the organizational communication seen through the use of politeness strategies by the management and administration representatives

The third and last section of this chapter aims to respond to the third research question: *What is the overall effectiveness of the organizational communication at UACS seen from the perspective of management and administration level?* This question stems from the fact that “one of the most effective ways to ensure and accomplish communication is the use of politeness strategies.” (Shabeeb and

Jibreen, 2008). Having in mind this, in both questionnaires the answers that the participants provided will be analysed from the point of politeness in order to see the effectiveness of the communication process in the organization. When using speech acts, the level of politeness can be measured according to many strategies that are used in different speech acts. Each speech act that is investigated here will be analysed through its own politeness strategies, except for the speech act of compliment which is considered to be politeness strategy itself in communication, or as Al-Azzawi (2011) says in his study about compliments: “Politeness can be expressed in many ways but paying a compliment is one of the most obvious.”

The parameters according to which the politeness level was determined in the speech acts of request and apology are shown in Table 14 below. This table was put together by the authors, based on the findings about the link between directness strategies and politeness level, in the works of Aydin (2013), Clark and Schunk (1980), and Cohen and Olshtain, 1983. (cited in Aydin, 2013).

The first part of this section will analyse the level of politeness in the use of the speech act of request. The analysis will be done based on three categories: first, the politeness level in the language used by the management group in horizontal and downward communication in the case of the speech act of request (see Table 15); second, the politeness level in the language used by the administration group

Table 14

Levels of politeness in the use of the speech acts of request and apology according to speech act strategy

Speech act	Strategy	Politeness level
Request	Direct request	Less polite
	Indirect request	Polite
	Declarative form	Less polite
	Interrogative form	Polite
	Imperative form	The least polite
	Imposition	Relatively polite
	Ability	Relatively polite
	Memory	Less polite
	Permission	The Politest
	Obligation	The least polite
	Hearer oriented	Less polite
	Speaker oriented	Polite
	Speaker and hearer oriented	Relatively polite
	Impersonal orientation	The politest
Apology	Direct apology	Less polite
	Indirect apology	Polite
	Explanation	Less polite
	Responsibility	Relatively polite
	Repair	Polite
	Promise of forbearance	The politest

Table 15

Use of politeness strategies by the management representatives in downward and horizontal communication in the speech act of request

Politeness level when using the speech act of request	Management representatives			
	Downward communication		Horizontal communication	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Politest	1	4.55%	1	4.35%
Polite	5	22.73%	10	43.48%
Relatively polite	3	13.64%	4	17.39%
Less polite	12	54.55%	8	34.78%
Least polite	1	4.55%	/	/

in horizontal and upward communication (see Table 16); and the last one is the overall politeness level in the language used by both groups in the case of request (see Table 17).

Table 15 presents the results from the responses of the management representatives in both instances. In the scenario with their subordinates, the majority of 54.55% used less polite strategy, and 22.73% used polite strategy. In the second scenario, where they used the speech act of request in horizontal communication, the majority or 43.48% used polite strategy and 34.78% used less polite strategy. Nobody in this scenario used impolite strategy.

The results from the responses of the administration representatives are shown in Table 16. The first column shows the politeness level in their request in upward

communication, and the second column shows the politeness level in horizontal communication. In upward communication, the majority of the administration representatives or 53.33% used the polite strategy, whereas when requesting something from their fellow colleagues on the same hierarchical level, 62.5% of this group used less polite strategy.

In the last table for this speech act, the overall use of the politeness strategies by both groups is shown. The responses show that the majority of the management representatives or 44.44% used the less polite strategy and 33.33% of them used the polite strategy. In the second group, the majority 48.39% used the less polite strategy and 41.94% used the polite strategy. There is no application of the impolite strategy in this group when using the speech act of request.

Table 16

Use of politeness strategies by the administration representatives in upward and horizontal communication in the speech act of request

<i>Administration representatives</i>				
<i>Politeness level when using the speech act of request</i>	<i>Upward communication</i>		<i>Horizontal communication</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Politest	2	13.33%	/	/
Polite	8	53.33%	5	31.25%
Relatively polite	/	/	1	6.25%
Less polite	5	33.33%	10	62.5%
Least polite	/	/	/	/

Table 17

Overall use of politeness strategies by management and administration representatives in the speech act of request

<i>Overall use of politeness strategies</i>				
<i>Politeness level when using the speech act of request</i>	<i>Management representatives</i>		<i>Administration representatives</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Politest	2	4.44%	2	6.45%
Polite	15	33.33%	13	41.94%
Relatively polite	7	15.56%	1	3.23%
Less polite	20	44.44%	15	48.39%
Least polite	1	2.22%	/	/

The second speech act to be analysed in terms of politeness levels is the speech act of apology. Same as with the speech act of request, the level of politeness that is applied when using the speech act of apology will be scaled from the politest to the least polite or impolite. This will be shown in three sections: first the use of politeness strategies by the management group in both scenarios (see Table 18), then the use of politeness strategies by the administration group in both scenarios (see Table 19) and, lastly, the overall use of the politeness strategies by both groups (see Table 20).

Table 18 gives the results from the responses of the management representatives in the cases of using the speech act of apology in horizontal and downward communication. In downward commu-

nication, the management representatives used two politeness strategies: one is the polite strategy used by the majority of the participants or 53.85%, and the less polite strategy used by 46.15% of the participants. In the second scenario, when apologizing to their fellow colleagues, management representatives used the less polite strategy in 72.73% of the cases and polite strategy in 27.27% of the cases.

Table 19 presents the results received from the responses of the administration representatives in both scenarios. The first column gives the responses in upward communication, and the second column gives the responses in horizontal communication. Namely, the majority 46.15% of the participants used the less polite strategy in their apologies to their

Table 18

Use of politeness strategies by the management representatives in downward and horizontal communication in the speech act of apology

Management group				
<i>Politeness level when using the speech act of apology</i>	<i>Downward communication</i>		<i>Horizontal communication</i>	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Politest	/	/	/	/
Polite	7	53.85%	3	27.27%
Relatively polite	/	/	/	/
Less polite	6	46.15%	8	72.73%
Least polite	/	/	/	/

Table 19

Use of politeness strategies by the administration representatives in upward and horizontal communication in the speech act of apology

Administration group				
<i>Politeness level when using the speech act of apology</i>	<i>Upward communication</i>		<i>Horizontal communication</i>	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Politest	1	7.69%	2	16.67%
Polite	5	38.46%	2	16.67%
Relatively polite	1	7.69%	/	/
Less polite	6	46.15%	8	66.67%
Least polite	/	/	/	/

superiors, and 38.46% of them used the polite strategy. In the second scenario, where they apologized to a fellow colleague, the numbers show that the majority of them or 66.67% used the less polite strategy, and the rest are equally divided between polite and the politest strategy with 16.67% for each strategy.

The last table in the case of the speech act of apology presents the overall use of the politeness strategies by both groups. In the case of the management group, the responses indicated that the majority of 58.33% would use the less polite strategy when apologizing to a colleague at the workplace, regardless of the hierarchy. In the case of the administration group, again the majority or 56% would use the less polite strategy.

As mentioned earlier, in the case of the speech act of compliment, there will be no scaled analysis of the politeness strategies used as in the previous two speech acts since the speech act itself is considered to be politeness strategy in communication. Since all the participants in both groups have used the speech act of compliment, we will consider that 100% of them use the polite strategy in communication and as such it will be added to the statistics.

Table 21 presents the overall use of politeness strategies by all participants. The results show that the polite and less polite strategies are the ones mostly used in the overall communication process, or with numbers - 46.32% go for the less polite strategy and 41.18% go for the polite strategy.

Table 20

Overall use of politeness strategies by management and administration representatives in the speech act of apology

<i>Overall use of politeness strategies</i>				
<i>Politeness level when using the speech act of apology</i>	<i>Management group</i>		<i>Administration group</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Politest	/		3	12%
Polite	10	41.67%	7	28%
Relatively polite	/	/	1	4%
Less polite	14	58.33%	14	56%
Least polite	/	/	/	/

Table 21

Overall use of politeness strategies in the organizational communication seen through the speech acts of request, apology and compliment

<i>Overall use of politeness strategies in the organizational communication at UACS</i>		
<i>Politeness level in the speech acts of request, apology and compliment</i>	<i>All participants</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Politest	7	5.15%
Polite	56	41.18%
Relatively polite	9	6.62%
Less polite	63	46.32%
Least polite	1	0.74%

Figure 5

shows a visual presentation of the use of politeness strategies in the organizational communication at UACS through the use of the speech acts of request, apology and compliment.

As mentioned earlier, in the case of the speech act of compliment, there will be no scaled analysis of the politeness strategies used as in the previous two speech acts since the speech act itself is considered to be politeness strategy in communication. Since all the participants in both groups have used the speech act of compliment, we will consider that 100% of them use the polite strategy in communication and as such it will be added to the statistics.

Table 21 presents the overall use of politeness strategies by all participants. The results show that the polite and less polite strategies are the ones mostly used in the overall communication process, or with numbers - 46.32% go for the less polite strategy and 41.18% go for the polite strategy.

DISCUSSION

This section describes the data analysis based on the results that are presented in the previous section. The analysis will be done in three subsections as answers to the research questions.

RQ1: WHICH DIRECTNESS STRATEGY IS APPLIED WHEN USING THE SPEECH ACTS OF REQUEST, APOLOGY, AND COMPLIMENT IN UPWARD, DOWNWARD AND HORIZONTAL COMMUNICATION?

The directness strategy in most of the speech acts is the main distinction between polite or less polite communication. Since this study is focused on organizational communication in general and in particular at UACS as a case organization, the analysis of the data will be conducted in the direction of what it means to have effective communication in an organizational setting. Jan et al. (2015) claim that “higher level of indirectness may result in higher level of politeness”.

The use of directness strategy in the speech acts of request, apology and compliment in downward communication

The first section will focus on the use of directness strategies in downward communication. The results show that the management representatives mostly use the direct strategy with the speech acts of apology and compliment, and indirect

strategy when using the speech act of request. If we see the overall use of directness strategy in the three speech acts, the majority of the participants use the direct strategy when communicating with their subordinates. According to the theory that direct is less polite and indirect is more polite, these results show that the management representatives are being polite when they request something from their employees.

The use of directness strategy in the speech acts of request, apology and compliment in upward communication

In the case of upward communication, or the use of these speech acts by the administration group directed towards their superiors, the results show a bit different picture than in the case of the management group, which, considering the hierarchy is to be expected up to a certain level. Namely, the representatives of the administration mainly use the indirect strategy when using the speech acts of request, apology and compliment with their superiors. This indicates that the majority of the administration group would use more polite strategy when using these three speech acts with their superiors. If these results are analysed according to the theoretical parameters, it is expected that the employees that are on the lower hierarchical level would use more polite strategies, to show respect and avoid any possible threatening feeling of the listener (in the case, the superior).

The use of directness strategy in the speech acts of request, apology and compliment in horizontal communication

In the case with horizontal communication, all the responses from both groups will be analysed at one time, and as a whole. In this scenario, the participants needed to use the speech act of request, apology and compliment with their fellow colleagues on the same hierarchical level. When the participants had to request

something from their colleagues, they mostly used the indirect strategy, or the more polite strategy, and if considering that the particular request in the scenario is in the form of asking for a favour, the polite strategy is expected to be used. In the use of the other two speech acts, the majority used the indirect strategy in the case of apology and the direct strategy in the case of compliment. If we take into consideration the politeness factor in the process of apologizing, then yes, it is a better choice when apologizing for something. Overall, in all three speech acts, when communicating with their fellow colleagues, the employees at UACS use the direct strategy, which does not necessarily mean a less polite strategy, but a strategy to be used among people who are familiar to each other.

RQ2: WHAT ARE THE DIFFERENCES OR SIMILARITIES WHEN USING THE SPEECH ACTS OF REQUEST, APOLOGY AND COMPLIMENT BETWEEN THE MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION REPRESENTATIVES?

Since the effectiveness of the organizational communication depends on each employee, regardless of the hierarchical level, it is important to see if there are any differences or/and similarities in the language used between the two investigated groups who belong to a different hierarchical level, and if these differences or/and similarities somehow influence on the effectiveness of the overall communication.

Comparison in the use of the speech act of request between the management and administration representatives

Levinson and Brown (1978), cited in Blum-Kulka and Olshtain (1984), defined requests as face-threatening speech acts (p. 201), or, in other words, “by making a request, the speaker impinges on the hearer’s claim to freedom of action and freedom from imposition”. Hence, for a communication process to be effective,

the speaker should try to minimize the imposition effect of the request. One certain way to do this is to apply the indirect strategy when using this speech act. The parameters according to which the request as speech act is analysed are all connected on the basis of being polite when uttering a certain speech act or the directness strategy.

When using the speech act of request in their overall use, the management representatives mostly use the indirect request or the more polite form of the speech act. In terms of the form of the request, half of them used declarative form and the other half used interrogative form. The declarative form is considered to be in the middle of politeness when taking into account the three syntactic forms: the interrogative, the declarative and the imperative form. According to Blum-Kulka and Olshtain (1984, p. 203), the speaker can use syntactic downgraders to down tone the imposition that the speech act of request is making. Hence, if we compare “*Do it!* And “*Will you, do it?*” the difference in the imposition is obvious. Therefore, if we take into consideration this theoretical view with regards to the syntax of the utterance, the management representatives use the polite and less polite form when using the speech act of request. When it comes to the indirect request, there are strategies that scale the politeness level from the most to the least polite strategy. Namely, in this categorization, the management representatives responded with the relatively polite strategies in almost 67% of the cases, which means that the effectiveness of communicating the speech act of request from this point is high. The last parameter according to which the effectiveness of the request is measured in this study is the point of orientation. The majority in this category or 83.33% of the participants responded with hearer orientation which is the less polite strategy when using the speech act of request, since it places the pressure on the hearer for the performance of the re-

quested action. However, if the strategies used in the previous categories are taken into consideration, that is, all of them are either polite or relatively polite, then it is safe to say that the management representative communicate effectively when using the speech act of request with their fellow colleagues and their subordinates.

Compared to the management group in the case of the speech act of request, the administration group uses both the direct and indirect strategy almost the same, or 55.56% go for the direct strategy and 44.44% go for the indirect strategy. However, if we see the separate responses in the case with their superiors and in the case with their fellow colleagues, the results say that almost everyone or 80% of them would use the direct strategy with their fellow colleagues and 75% of them would use the indirect, started with their superiors. This says that these respondents are more comfortable with their fellow colleagues and they prefer to use direct requests and, on the other hand, they respect the hierarchy and use the more polite strategy when requesting something from their superiors. In the case of the syntactic form of the request, the results are almost equally divided between the declarative and interrogative form, which indicates again the use of polite and relatively polite strategy. When it comes to the strategies for those who have used the indirect request, 50% of the respondents answered with the permission strategy which is the politest one, and the other half are divided between the ability and commitment strategies which are relatively polite and less polite respectively. Considering that the indirect strategy itself is the polite strategy, and that 75% of the participants responded with a polite strategy, then it is safe to say that in this section they have used effective or polite communication. In the last part of this comparison, the results show that the majority of the participants or almost 56% have used the hearer-oriented strategy and the rest of them have used the

speaker orientation. Here it is important to mention that the speaker-orientation strategy was 100% used in the case with the superiors, which again shows the respect toward the hierarchy, that is the use of the more polite strategy, and the hearer orientation was used 100% in the case with their fellow colleagues which shows the informality and comfort with their colleagues on the same hierarchical level.

Comparison in the use of the speech act of apology between the management and administration representatives

According to Aydin (2013), the rule for directness applies with this speech acts as well, or the more direct the apology, the less polite and vice versa. The apologies in this paper were analysed through two aspects, one is direct – indirect apology based on the study of Aydin (2013), and the other is through the scale of directness strategies of Cohen and Olshtain, 1983, (cited in Aydin, 2013) that go from the most direct or explicit apology to the least direct one.

Having into consideration these parameters, both groups of respondents have mostly used the direct apology in terms of (in) directness. The direct apology is not necessarily the “negative” strategy for apology, but is a better one when it comes to clarity of the message. The indirect apology can often be ambiguous for the hearer. In terms of the scale of directness strategies, the management’s group majority responded with the repair strategy which is almost at the bottom of directness and the administration group responded differently mostly with the explanation strategy which is at the top of the directness scale. According to the theory, the management group is more effective in communicating an apology in this section as they offered to repair whatever they did wrong, comparing to the administration group who mostly offered only an explanation for the wrong doing.

Comparison in the use of the speech act of compliment between the management and administration representatives

As a speech act, the compliment act will not be analysed from the politeness point of view as the previous two speech acts, since the speech act itself is a politeness strategy in communication. Still, when using the compliment as a speech act, there are several strategies that can be applied which will determine the meaning and the message sent with it. Farenkia (2012) recognizes three strategies to express compliments: direct compliments, indirect compliments and compliments with external modification. Direct compliments are expressed in an unambiguous or explicit manner with positive note, expressed directly to the addressee. Indirect compliments are expressed in a more ambiguous way that requires certain level of supposition by the addressee in order to get the intended meaning of the compliment. The third strategy, external modification, refers to the acts that are said before or after the direct compliments, serving a purpose of intensifying or mitigating. As per Farenkia’s findings, the most commonly used compliment strategy is the direct strategy. Since the compliments are a very important tool in motivating employees and keeping a positive working environment, especially in downward communication, it is an essential speech act in the organizational communication that needs to be effective.

In the scenario where the speech act of compliment had to be used, the management group mostly used the direct strategy and the external modification strategy. Namely, 50% of the participants used the direct strategy with their subordinates, which shows that they want to be explicit when giving a compliment to a subordinate, so that the listener feels recognized and valued. In the case with their fellow colleagues, 50% of the participants responded with a compliment with external modification, which is an

intensified direct compliment, again a positive strategy to use when communicating a compliment. On the other hand, the administration group, in the case with their superiors, mostly responded with indirect strategy when complimenting on the success of their superior, which is not the case when using this speech act with their fellow colleagues. The numbers show that 60% of them used direct strategy when complimenting a colleague. If the whole communication of the administration group to their superiors is taken into consideration, then it is safe to say that those 60% in giving an indirect compliment show a respect towards a superior and hierarchical inferiority. This is even clearer given the fact that 60% of them used the direct strategy with their fellow colleagues. In terms of complexity, every participant made an effort to give a complex compliment with a lot of adjectives and positivity.

RQ3: WHAT IS THE OVERALL EFFECTIVENESS OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL COMMUNICATION AT UACS SEEN FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION LEVEL?

The use of politeness strategies in the speech act of request

When the speech act of request is used in downward communication, even though by definition this speech act is face threatening, it can be used with a strategy that down tones that imposition. The superiors at UACS, when using the speech act of request with their subordinates, mostly (almost 55%) applied the less polite strategy, opposing to almost 23% of them who used the polite strategy. With these results into consideration and the actual numbers from the responses of the participants, it is clear that the management is effectively communicating the speech act of request with their subordinates.

On the other hand, in the case with their fellow colleagues, the majority (almost 44%) of them responded with polite

strategy, and almost 35% responded with the less polite strategy. This again shows the comfort of the participants with a fellow colleague, or in other words, in a situation where the authority is on the same level, the level of comfort is higher in the communication.

In the case with the administration group, the results are very distinct from the ones of the management group. Namely, in the scenario with the colleagues from the same hierarchical level, the results show that almost 63% of the participants used the less polite strategy, and in the scenario with their superiors, almost 54% used the polite strategy. Here again, the administration is communicating with their superiors, as expected - with higher politeness considering the hierarchical positions of both groups.

The use of politeness strategies in the speech act of apology

The politeness in the speech act of apology is distinguished in the same manner as in the request, that is the more direct and explicit the apology, the less polite, and the more indirect the apology, the more polite it is. In terms of directness of the apology, there are several strategies that determine the level of directness, hence the level of politeness (see Table 15).

The management representatives in the scenario where they needed to apologize to their subordinate, mostly (almost 54%) used the polite strategy to do so. On the other hand, in the scenario with their fellow colleague, a big majority of almost 73% used the less polite strategy. These results show that the management representatives pay little more attention to the language used when apologizing to their subordinates despite the fact that they are on the superior position, which shows a great appreciation and respect towards their subordinates, which on some other level is a great way to keep the unity and respect between the two hierarchical

levels. While in the case with their fellow colleagues, the results show a little more comfort when expressing an apology.

In the case of the administration group, the results differ from those of their superiors. Specifically, in the scenario where they needed to apologize to their superior, almost 47% of them apologized with a less polite strategy and almost 39% with a polite strategy. In the scenario with their fellow colleagues, the majority of almost 67% answered with a less polite strategy. Even though both are polite strategies in general, still, in the case of upward communication, especially when it comes to apologizing to a superior, for the communication to be effective, the polite strategy should have had the majority of the answers. Other than that, the strategy used with their fellow colleagues, as in the case with the management representatives, is expected and acceptable.

Overall use of politeness strategies at UACS

The overall use of politeness strategies by all the participants or on the level of organization at UACS is represented through almost 46.32% of using the less polite strategies, and 41.18% of using the polite strategies of the speech acts in question (see Figure 4). These numbers show that the difference between the less polite and polite answers is very small, and having in mind that both strategies are actually polite strategies, only distinguished by one level, then it is safe to say that the employees at UACS represented by the management and administration group do communicate effectively when using the speech acts of request, apology and compliment.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicate that the employees at UACS represented by the participants of both management and administration group communicate effectively. If conclusions are to be

made separately by the type of communication (downward, upward and horizontal), then the findings show that in downward communication, the management representatives use the indirect strategy with the speech acts of apology and compliment, which shows that they aim for more politeness in the cases of these speech acts, therefore higher effectiveness. Positive emphasis is put on the management group when using the speech act of request or giving tasks to their subordinates, when they mostly used an indirect strategy, which indicates great consideration towards their colleagues and ensures politeness rather than face threatening and that is one of the essential strategies to ensure employee motivation and satisfaction. In the case of upward communication, the findings show that administration representatives use the direct strategy when apologizing and complimenting and the indirect strategy when requesting something from their superiors. This choice of strategies indicates that this hierarchical level aims for politeness when requesting something from their superiors, which is expected considering the hierarchy, and aims for clarity when apologizing and complimenting in the case of the upward communication. The findings show that, overall, both hierarchical groups use the direct strategies with these speech acts, which is an indication of familiarity and higher comfort in the communication process between colleagues that are on the same hierarchical level. Finally, the results from the collected data show that in downward communication the mostly used strategy is the direct one, in upward communication the mostly used strategy is the indirect one, and in horizontal communication the mostly used strategy is the direct strategy, which leads to a general conclusion that the communication process at UACS seen through the representatives of both hierarchical levels is effective and satisfactory.

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APPENDIX A: SITUATIONAL QUESTIONNAIRE (ADMINISTRATION REPRESENTATIVES)

RESPECTED PARTICIPANTS,

As part of the research on the use of speech acts in organizational communication and their effect on organizational performance, conducted for the purpose of the master thesis named “Speech Acts of Requests, Apologies, and Compliments in Organizational Communication: Case Study of University American College Skopje”, I, Vesna Hristova, post-graduate student at the School of Foreign Languages at UACS, am kindly asking for your help and input by completing this questionnaire with your pragmatic use of the language in the situations given below. The goal of this questionnaire is to provide us with data that will show the actual use of the speech acts that are subject to this study and the strategies applied when expressing them, which will further allow us to connect the theory with the practical use of these speech acts and draw a conclusion accordingly. Your input will help this research by obtaining information about the pragmatic side of the language use in Macedonian organization. There is no need for you to write your name, as this questionnaire is anonymous. The information obtained will be kept secret and used only for the purpose of this academic research. I would like to thank you in advance for your help and cooperation.

Directions: Please read the situations given below. There are two situations for each speech act that is subject to this research, one that implies communication with your fellow colleagues and one that implies communication with your superiors. Please answer to each situation as you would normally do, by using a language that you normally use in your daily communication with your colleagues and superiors.

Situation 1a (apology speech act, subordinate to superior)

Imagine that your superior has asked you to finish a task of high importance in less time than normally needed for this task. This would require you to stay later at work; however, you had an important private issue so you had to leave work earlier than you anticipated. The next day your superior calls and asks for the papers, but you are not done yet. What do you say?

Situation 1b (apology speech act, same level)

Your colleague has asked you to take over her tasks for the day as she needs to go to the doctor and she is not sure if she will be able to come back to work today. You promised her that you would do it; however, having a lot of your own tasks for the day you completely forgot about her. The next day she asks for an explanation why you didn't do as promised. What do you say?

Situation 2a (request speech act, subordinate to superior)

You need some days off to attend to some personal matters. Perhaps this is not the best time to ask this as it is a hectic period at work, but you have to finish these matters. What do you say to your boss?

Situation 2b (request speech act, same level)

You have a long report to finish for the meeting of the board of directors, which is due today, and you still have daily assignments that you will not be able to complete. You need to ask your colleague to help you so you can finish the report on time. What do you say to your colleague?

Situation 3a (compliment speech act, subordinate to superior)

Your immediate supervisor has been promoted to a higher management level. This means you will not be working directly with her in the future, but you are

still very happy for her. What do you say to compliment her success?

Situation 3b (compliment speech act, same level)

Imagine that your colleague has been promoted to your supervisor as per accomplishments and seniority within the organizations. She came happy to announce the news to you. What do you say?

Thank you!

**APPENDIX B:
SITUATIONAL QUESTIONNAIRE
(MANAGEMENT REPRESENTATIVES)**

RESPECTED PARTICIPANTS,

As part of the research on the use of speech acts in organizational communication and their effect on organizational performance, conducted for the purpose of the master thesis named “Speech Acts of Requests, Apologies, and Compliments in Organizational Communication: Case Study of University American College Skopje”, I, Vesna Hristova, post-graduate student at the School of Foreign Languages at UACS, am kindly asking for your help and input by completing this questionnaire with your pragmatic use of the language in the situations given below. The goal of this questionnaire is to provide us with data that will show the actual use of the speech acts that are subject to this study and the strategies applied when expressing them, which will further allow us to connect the theory with the practical use of these speech acts and draw a conclusion accordingly. Your input will help this research by obtaining information about the pragmatic side of the language use in Macedonian organization. There is no need for you to write your name, as this questionnaire is anonymous. The information obtained will be kept secret and used only for the purpose of this academic research. I would like to thank you in advance for your help and cooperation.

Directions: Please read the situations given below. There are two situations for each speech act that is subject to this research, one that implies communication with your fellow colleagues and one that implies communication with your subordinates. Please answer to each situation as you would normally do, by using a language that you normally use in your daily communication with your colleagues and subordinates.

Situation 1a (apology speech act, superior to subordinate)

Imagine an employee has asked a certain document from you to help her with bank loan procedures. You have promised to do it; however, you’ve been busy working and forgot. The employee came to your office on the agreed date to collect the document. What do you say?

Situation 1b (apology speech act, same level)

The class schedule for the month has come out and you have classes earlier in the month unlike your fellow colleague whose classes are later in the month. She has asked you to switch the class dates because she wants to travel earlier in the month. Unfortunately, you are not able to switch the dates since you already made some plans yourself. What do you say to your colleague?

Situation 2a (request speech act, superior to subordinate)

Imagine you need a certain task done by tomorrow, and you have to request from an administration employee to do it; however, you are aware that she will need to stay over time today in order to finish it by tomorrow. What do you say to the employee?

Situation 2b (request speech act, same level)

You have an exam in two days; however, some important meeting has come up and you are not able to attend the exam. It is late to reschedule the exam, so you

decide to ask your fellow colleague to investigate it instead of you. What do you say to your colleague?

Situation 3a (compliment speech act, superior to subordinate)

Imagine that some of your employees has made an extra effort to finish a job task in a way that goes beyond her job description. You are happy with this employee and you want to compliment her on the job well done. What do you say?

Situation 3b (compliment speech act, same level)

Your colleague has won a fellowship at a very respectable university out of the country. You have worked with him for many years and you are happy he finally got an award for his hard work. He comes to your office to share the good news. What do you say to him?

Thank you!